

Supplementary Information:

Over 31%-Efficient Perovskite-TOPCon Solar Cells Enabled by AlO_x -based Hydrogenation and Front Sub-micron Texturing

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Implied-Voc and contact resistivity evolution with bottom cell process flow

Firstly, we investigated the compatibility of our poly-Si(n) contact with the process flow of the TOPCon² bottom cell. The Fig.S1 presents the iV_{oc} and lifetime evaluated by PCD at different processing steps for three hydrogenation treatments; control (i.e., no hydrogenation), AlO_x /Hotplate and SiN_x /firing for flat and nanotextured surfaces (on symmetrical samples structures).

On flat surfaces, the hydrogenation mechanism has only a limited influence on the iV_{oc} . For both SiN_x and AlO_x based treatment, high iV_{oc} values can be reached and there is only limited degradation after the HF etching of the H-rich layers. Both hydrogenation treatment results in higher passivation than the control samples. However, after the sputtering step, all samples have more or less the same iV_{oc} .

On nanotextured surfaces, the standard hydrogenation (i.e. SiN_x /firing) leads to high passivation but the long HF exposure to remove the SiN_x layer strongly damages the interfacial oxide leading to poor iV_{oc} after etching further reduced by sputtering the ITO layer on top. Replacing the SiN_x /firing by the deposition of a thin (10 nm) AlO_x allows to reach higher passivation after hydrogenation and the short HF exposure needed to etch the AlO_x does not degrade the passivation. This leads to an iV_{oc} of ~ 737 mV after HF treatment, which is then reduced as well during the ITO sputtering.

Figure S1. Evolution of the implied V_{oc} for different hydrogenation mechanism on flat and nanotextured surfaces.

To recover the passivation after ITO sputtering, a thermal curing step is introduced. Fig.S2 shows the evolution of the effective lifetime after different processing step. The highest lifetime is achieved after hydrogenation (blue curve) followed by a strong reduction after HF

and ITO sputtering (orange curve). The hotplate curing allows to recover the passivation loss (brown curve), resulting in passivation level similar or higher than in the initial stage.

Figure S2. Evolution of the minority carrier lifetime after the different processing steps.

We monitor the contact resistivity of the Ag/ITO/poly-Si/c-Si stack with varying curing temperatures. We find that contact resistivity increases with curing temperature, reaching up to 100 $m\Omega\cdot cm^2$ (Fig.S3). Given that these layers are intended for full-area deposition, this level of resistivity is still acceptable for tandem applications with reduced current density. In an attempt to reduce sputter-induced damage, we studied the impact of the UV-O₃ exposure time on the interfacial SiO_x. We find that increased UV-O₃ exposure time results in greater sensitivity to sputtering damage but the mechanism behind this behavior is not yet understood.

Figure S3. Contact resistivity change for different tunnel oxide formation time (UV-O₃ treatment) and various post-deposition curing temperature.

Bottom cell processing sequence validation in single junctions

To validate our findings at the cell level, we fabricated single-junction solar cells on fully flat wafers and tested different curing temperatures to reduce sputtering damage. At the rear we

apply an ITO/Ag stack, at the front an ITO layer is sputtered, followed by evaporation of an Ag grid to define cells with a 1.0 cm² active area. Since etching the SiN_x layer reduced passivation to levels observed after annealing, we also fabricated cells without hydrogenation (i.e., no SiN_x/firing/HF) treatment which simplifies the process flow.

Fig.S4 presents the IV parameters of these devices before and after curing at various temperatures. Before curing, the V_{oc} is considerably lower than the iV_{oc}, further highlighting the adverse effect of sputtering. Curing up to 350°C successfully recovers this damage, yielding a maximum V_{oc} of 708 mV. The FF initially improves, reaching 79% due to reduced recombination. However, beyond 350°C, FF degrades and at 400°C, strong S-shaped distortions appear in the IV curves due to increased contact resistivity. High curing temperatures increase J_{sc}, likely due to enhanced ITO transparency. The maximum efficiency of 19% is achieved with a curing temperature of 300°C, balancing V_{oc}, FF and J_{sc} optimally. Additionally, we observe that cells without hydrogenation show only minor efficiency loss compared to the ones with hydrogenation.

Figure S4. Main solar cell parameters (V_{oc}, J_{sc}, FF and PCE) evolution after different post-fabrication curing steps on fully flat wafers.

Efficiency evolution over several tandem batches

Figs. S1 and S2 illustrate the efficiency evolution of the tandem devices across several batches. The initial batch primarily served to debug the bottom cell fabrication process, with performance significantly limited by high sputtering damage that reduced the iV_{oc} of the bottom cells.

For the second batch, we optimized the ITO post-deposition curing step and incorporated a higher top cell bandgap, leading to improved results. Batches 3 and 4 focused on testing the optimized bottom

cell curing on industrial CZ wafers with SiN_x hydrogenation treatment and FZ p-type wafers with AlO_x hydrogenation, respectively. Both batches utilized an identical top cell processing, employing the low E_g composition detailed below (our laboratory's baseline process for nanotextured bottom cells). *Batch 3*'s performance was mainly constrained by a very low J_{sc}, attributed to the thin (150 μm) wafers used. Conversely, *Batch 4* achieved comparable FF and J_{sc} to *Batch 2* but exhibited a lower Voc due to the lower top cell bandgap.

Figure 5. Efficiency evolution of PK-TOPCon tandem on flat wafers.

In *batch 1* of Fig.S2, “nano-pyramid” are used on the front side of the bottom cells. There is a huge spreading of the efficiency mainly due to the sensitivity of the poly-Si(n)/SiO_x passivating contact during the extended HF exposure to remove the H-rich SiN_x layer after hydrogenation. The passivation loss during that process was not constant for all bottom cell pixels. To prevent the strong passivation damage from the HF treatment, the 2nd batch was tried without hydrogenation, in this case all the bottom cells had similar iV_{oc} value around 670 mV limiting the V_{oc} of the tandem devices. With the introduction of the AlO_x hydrogenation, the iV_{oc} of the bottom cell (after ITO front and ITO/Ag rear sputtering + curing) is increased to 710 mV (*batch 3*) and 720 mV (*batch 4*) which then lead to an increase tandem efficiency.

Figure 6. Efficiency evolution of PK-TOPCon tandem on front nanotextured wafers.

Material and methods

Bottom-cell processing

Fig.S3 depicts the process flow to fabricate the bottom cell and the final tandem devices architectures. The bottom cells with passivating contacts were fabricated using a (100)-oriented, n-type float-zone crystalline silicon (c-Si) wafer, either fully flat or with front-side texturing. The wafers had a resistivity of approximately $2 \Omega\cdot\text{cm}$ and a thickness of $\sim 200 \mu\text{m}$. Single-side nanotexturing was achieved by depositing a silicon nitride (SiN_x) layer via plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition (PECVD) on one side, which acted as an etch mask during alkaline texturing in a KOH solution. After standard RCA-1 and RCA-2 cleaning, a thin passivating silicon oxide (SiO_x) layer ($\sim 1.2 \text{ nm}$) was formed by UV-O_3 exposure for 2 minutes. Doped polycrystalline silicon (poly-Si) layers were deposited via PECVD in a parallel-plate reactor (Kai-M) to form the carrier-selective contacts: phosphorus-doped (n-type) for the front and boron-doped (p-type) for the rear. For n-type doping, silicon tetrafluoride (SiF_4), phosphine (PH_3 , 2% diluted in hydrogen), and argon (Ar) were used, while silane (SiH_4), methane (CH_4), hydrogen (H_2), and boron trifluoride (BF_3) were employed for p-type doping. The deposition duration for the front n-doped layer was adjusted depending on the surface morphology (flat or nanotextured) to achieve a thickness of 15 nm. The rear p-type amorphous silicon layer was deposited to a thickness of 20 nm. A single annealing step was carried out at 850°C in a quartz tube furnace under an inert atmosphere to induce partial crystallization of the doped poly-Si layers and facilitate dopant diffusion into the SiO_x /wafer interface, thereby reducing contact resistivity. Hydrogenation was performed using either SiN_x or AlO_x -based layers. For the SiN_x approach, an 80 nm thick hydrogenated SiN_x ($\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$) layer was deposited on both sides of the wafer via PECVD using SiH_4 , ammonia (NH_3), and H_2 , followed by a rapid thermal process (RTP) at 800°C for 20 s in a belt furnace. For the AlO_x -based treatment, 5–10 nm of hydrogenated, non-stoichiometric aluminum oxide ($\text{AlO}_x\text{:H}$) was deposited by thermal atomic layer deposition (ALD) at 125°C using trimethylaluminum (TMA) and water (H_2O), followed by annealing on a hotplate at 400°C in ambient air. The hydrogen-rich layers ($\text{SiN}_x\text{:H}$ or $\text{AlO}_x\text{:H}$) were subsequently removed by wet etching in 5% hydrofluoric acid (HF) for 30 min and 30 s, respectively. The rear contact stack, consisting of 80 nm indium tin oxide (ITO) and 500 nm silver (Ag), was deposited via sputtering, followed by deposition of a 20 nm front-side ITO recombination layer. Both front and rear contacts were patterned using a shadow mask to define an active area of $1.0 \times 1.0 \text{ cm}^2$. To heal sputtering-induced damage, the bottom cell precursors were annealed in air for 15 minutes. Finally, the 4-inch wafers were laser-cut into $2.5 \times 2.5 \text{ cm}^2$ substrates.

Figure S7. Bottom cell process flow and tandem device architecture

Top-cell processing

SAM (e.g., Me-4PACz) solution (1 mg/mL) is spin-coated onto substrates for 100 μL with a program of 10 s resting time, 3000 rpm, 300 rpm/s. Then the substrates are annealed for 10 min at 115°C . To

improve the wetting, 0.1% SiO_x-np in EtOH (20 nm diameter) spin-coated for 100 μL with a program of 2000 rpm with 500 rpm/s for 30 s and annealed for 115 °C for 10 min²⁴. The absorber utilized in tandems is Cs_{0.05}(FA_{0.9}MA_{0.1})_{0.95}Pb(I_{0.80}Br_{0.20})₃ + 3% (MAPbCl₃). The absorber is fabricated with the one-step anti-solvent method. The molarity of the solution is 1.7M. 100 uL perovskite ink is spun at 3000 rpm for 40s with 300 rpm/s acceleration and when 10 s are left during the spin program, 250 μL of Anisole (Sigma Aldrich, >99%) is dropped onto the substrate. Then the samples are annealed at 100°C for 15-20 min inside the glovebox. 15-20 nm of C₆₀ (Creaphys, >99.9% - resublimed) is deposited via thermal evaporation with a rate of 0.2 Å/s. Then ALD-SnO_x is deposited at 95°C with pulse purge times of 0.3s / 6s / 0.1s / 6s for 150-175 cycles with TDMASn and H₂O sources. The utilized thicknesses for baseline devices are 20 nm measured with an ellipsometer on c-Si. After the ALD-SnO_x, 35 nm of IZrO with sheet resistance around 225 ohm/square is deposited from 4-inch 98% I₂O₃ + 2% ZrO target with deposition power of 70W and working pressure 2.7 μbar with ~0.14% of O₂ to Ar ratio. After the TCO, ~500 nm of Ag grid is evaporated with a rate of 2 Å/s which is followed by 100 nm evaporation of LiF or MgF_x with 1 Å/s rate in Angstrom thermal evaporator.

Characterization

JV

The 4PP measurement method is used. JV measurements were obtained using a two-lamp (Halogen and Xenon) class AAA WACOM sun simulator with an AM1.5G irradiance spectrum at 1.000 W/m². Three-point weight MPP measurements are performed using an in-house written LabVIEW code. For the measurement of tandem devices, before each measurement, the calibration of the AAA WACOM system is checked with three different certified cells with different spectral responses to minimize the spectral mismatch of the sources. Initially, to adjust the intensity of the Xe lamp, a calibrated encapsulated cell (WPVS – blue cell) containing a monocrystalline silicon solar cell, which is covered with a KG5-filter was used. Then to adjust the intensity of Ha lamp, a calibrated encapsulated cell (WPVS – red cell) containing a monocrystalline silicon solar cell, which is covered with a RG780-filter was used. Then, overall spectrum is checked with a calibrated encapsulated cell (WPVS without filter broadband – black cell). To further fine-adjust the intensity of the Ha lamp, a tandem cell within the fabricated batch was first measured by EQE, then the lamp intensity was adjusted to match the integrated EQE of the bottom cell with the measured J_{sc}, notably with the conditions in which the bottom cell is the current limiting cell. All calibrated Si cells are provided by Fraunhofer ISE. Then the tandem cells with ~1 cm² are measured with a scan rate of ~ 0.1V/s and using a 1 cm² shadow mask. A temperature-controlled (25 °C) brass chuck was used.

EQE

EQE spectra is measured with PV Tools LOANA system with full area illumination using the same shadow mask used in the JV measurements with 1 cm² active area. Hence, reported EQEs include shadowing losses from the Ag fingers. While measuring the perovskite sub-cell, device is illuminated with IR LED external light bias and 0.6V is applied. While measuring the Si sub-cell, device is illuminated with blue LED external light bias and 1.1V is applied.

Sample statistics and error analysis

For each condition (i.e. flat vs nanotextured), 6 tandem solar cells are produced from the same 4'' wafer, all of them are reported in the main figure of the paper as well as the median value and the standard deviation in the interval of confidence of 97% (3σ). The median and standard deviation are computed using the forward and reverse scan of the devices (with same architecture and processing steps). The champion devices reported values are extracted by averaging the forward and reverse scan IV-metrics.